

E5.6.2: Final design of data aggregation for self-optimization processes on network operations

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3 List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
BSON	Binary JSON
CDR	Call Detail Records
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
ETL	Extract Load Transform
EC-CDF	Empirical Complementary Cumulative Distribution Function
HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Life-cycle Management
MA-DRL	Multi-Agent Deep Reinforcement Learning
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
VNF	Virtual Network Function
OTLP	OpenTelemetry Protocol
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TSM	Time-Structured Merge
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications

4 Executive Summary

This deliverable summarizes the works carried out in task A5.2 of the project 6GENABLERS, IA para 6G: Ultra Automatización y Optimización, reference number TSI-063000-2021-10, which investigates aggregation methods for 6G network optimisation based on smart telemetry. **This deliverable is a sequel of the initial deliverable E5.2.2, which means that they complement each other while avoiding repetition.** After a brief introduction, the report recalls the concept of data aggregation and describes the corresponding functionalities, including the adopted design/code snippet. The report then reviews the integration with Kubeflow pipelines toward a deployment for 6G optimisation.

5 Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of next-generation networks, the integration of self-optimization processes is essential for maintaining operational efficiency, scalability, and adaptability. In this deliverable we present a comprehensive framework for using data aggregation as a foundational element in a hybrid architecture comprising both Cloud and Edge Kubernetes clusters. This document explores the pivotal role of data aggregation in consolidating diverse telemetry streams, enabling real-time decision-making, and supporting machine learning (ML)-driven automation. Through statistical methodologies, advanced pipelines, and a closed-loop design, the proposed architecture in 6G Enablers-AI closes the gap between data collection and actions. It highlights the strategic value of integrating robust aggregation mechanisms with cutting-edge ML workflows to optimize network operations, ensuring resilience and performance in increasingly complex environments.

6 Monitoring Data Aggregation

6.1 Importance of Data Aggregation

Data aggregation serves as the backbone of self-optimization processes in network operations, enabling the seamless consolidation of different data streams into structured actions. In a hybrid architecture comprising a cloud cluster and an Edge Kubernetes cluster, as the one present in 6GEnablers-AI, aggregation becomes a critical enabler for maintaining coherence, operational efficiency, and informed decision-making. It allows the integration of diverse data types—ranging from machine-generated metrics to application-level actions—into a unified framework that supports advanced analytics, anomaly detection, and predictive modelling. This capability is fundamental in ensuring the reliability and adaptability of both cloud and edge operations. The following description is based in Figure 1, where the 6G Enablers Cloud architecture is described.

Figure 1 6G Enablers-AI Architecture.

6.2 Functionalities of Data Aggregation

The aggregation process unites multi-source data flows across the cloud and edge environments. At its core, it transforms raw telemetry data into meaningful statistical summaries, feeds ML pipelines for training and inference, and drives observability dashboards for real-time operational insights. Within the cloud cluster, the Kubernetes aggregator node collects and processes host-level and Kubernetes metrics, sending this information to the observability backend. This backend not only provides a centralized view of system health but also serves as a conduit for processed data to be further utilized by the Feature Store and offline storage. The Feature Store acts as a bridge, linking aggregated data with ML models for both immediate inference and historical analysis.

At the edge, aggregation focuses on telemetry from the Holoportation application, Prometheus server, and client connector, integrating these inputs into the AI Ops entity. This distributed setup ensures the AI Ops entity can use both edge-specific metrics and actions derived from the cloud cluster's ML models. The Prometheus server further

enhances functionality by enabling time-series aggregation, supporting the detection of trends and the identification of deviations within localized edge operations.

6.3 Data Aggregation Workflow

Data aggregation, in the 6G Enablers-AI architecture, operates on three fundamental levels: collection, transformation, and utilization.

Collection:

In the cloud, host and Kubernetes metrics are captured via the Kubernetes cloud server aggregator, which pulls telemetry from nodes and containers. Simultaneously, data pipelines extract structured and unstructured datasets through the ETL process, linking directly to the offline store for persistent storage and future validation.

At the edge, the Prometheus server gathers time-series metrics from the Holoportation application and client connector, ensuring high-granularity telemetry suitable for localized analysis.

Transformation:

Raw telemetry and operational logs are processed by the observability backend and Feature Store in the cloud cluster. Data is cleaned, normalized, and encoded into formats compatible with downstream ML pipelines. Statistical aggregation techniques, including cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) and feature engineering processes, distill large-scale data into representative features for training and inference. In parallel, the AI Ops entity at the edge synthesizes telemetry from Prometheus and integrates it with ML inferences originating from the cloud, creating a feedback loop between the edge and cloud clusters.

The empirical CDF, mean and variance statistical aggregation has been designed as follows:

```
def sla_loss(x_data, lower_bound, model_function, precision=1e-6):  
    if len(x_data) == 0:  
        raise ValueError("Input data cannot be empty.")  
    if lower_bound < min(x_data) or lower_bound > max(x_data):  
        raise ValueError("Lower bound must be within the range of input data.")  
    try:  
        pred_values = model_function(x_data)  
    except Exception as e:  
        raise RuntimeError(f"Model function failed: {str(e)}")  
    if len(pred_values) == 0:  
        raise ValueError("Predicted values cannot be empty.")  
    empirical_dist = np.sort(pred_values) # Sort predictions for CDF calculation
```

```
cdf_value = np.searchsorted(empirical_dist, lower_bound, side='right') / len(empirical_dist)

mean_value = np.mean(empirical_dist)
variance = np.var(empirical_dist)

return {
    "cdf_value": round(cdf_value, int(-np.log10(precision))),
    "mean": mean_value,
    "variance": variance
}
```

Utilization:

Aggregated insights in the cloud feed real-time dashboards, providing operators with a consolidated view of system health, performance anomalies, and predictive forecasts. ML models trained on this aggregated data are deployed both for edge inference and cloud-side orchestration. At the edge, aggregated data informs adaptive operations of the Holoportation application and enables the AI Ops entity to execute autonomous optimizations based on real-time and historical trends.

In the architecture of 6G Enablers-AI, data aggregation is not merely a process but a unifying framework, bridging cloud and edge capabilities. It ensures the smooth flow of information across the system, fostering a high degree of resilience, scalability, and operational intelligence.

7 Data Pipelines

Data pipelines are the critical conduits that enable seamless data flow, processing, and utilization across the hybrid architecture of the cloud and Edge Kubernetes clusters. They ensure that raw data from diverse sources, such as telemetry systems, applications, and logs, is systematically transformed into clean, structured, and actionable inputs for machine learning (ML) and analytics tasks. In the context of self-optimization processes, data pipelines play an essential role in automating the preparation, transformation, and integration of data, ensuring the robustness and repeatability of ML workflows. This capability is essential for the scalability of the system, supporting both real-time and batch processing requirements while maintaining high data integrity and consistency.

7.1 Functionality of Data Pipelines

Data pipelines within the 6G Enablers-AI environment provide the foundation for the lifecycle of data, from initial ingestion to final consumption by ML models, observability tools, and AI-driven optimization processes. In the cloud cluster, Kubeflow Pipelines orchestrate the flow of data for ML model training and inference. These pipelines connect multiple stages, including data preprocessing, feature extraction, model training, hyperparameter tuning, and deployment. At the edge, data pipelines streamline the transfer and integration of telemetry data with cloud-derived actions, ensuring efficient bi-directional communication between the cloud and edge environments.

The pipelines not only automate the flow of data but also enable modularity, reusability, and traceability, which are crucial for managing complex workflows in dynamic network environments. By using Kubeflow Pipelines, the cloud system ensures that ML workflows are not only efficient but also reproducible, allowing operators to track and validate each stage of the process.

7.2 Working with Data Pipelines

Data pipelines in the 6G Enablers-AI architecture operate through three interconnected phases: ingestion, processing, and delivery.

Ingestion:

In the cloud cluster, raw data is ingested from multiple sources, including host and Kubernetes metrics aggregated by the Kubernetes cloud server, as well as data streams extracted by the ETL process connected to the offline store. The ETL process ensures that ingested data is cleaned, filtered, and formatted for downstream processing.

At the edge, data pipelines ingest real-time telemetry from the Holoportation application and Prometheus server. This telemetry data is combined with client connector insights to create a comprehensive view of edge-specific operations.

Processing:

Within the cloud, Kubeflow Pipelines manage the ML workflow. Data is preprocessed through feature engineering steps, including normalization,

scaling, and the extraction of key statistical features. These features are stored in the Feature Store, which acts as a central repository linking data to ML models for both training and inference. Data pipelines also handle the transformation of historical data stored in the offline store into training datasets. This enables the continuous improvement of ML models by incorporating new patterns and trends.

At the edge, telemetry data is processed to generate low-latency insights that feed directly into the AI Ops entity. The processed data at the edge is periodically synchronized with the cloud to maintain alignment with global models and insights.

Delivery:

In the cloud cluster, processed data is delivered to multiple endpoints, including the ML model pipelines for training and inference tasks and the observability backend, where data is visualized and monitored through dashboards. Additionally, the Feature Store and offline store, ensuring that the data is accessible for both real-time and historical analysis. At the edge, processed telemetry and model inference results are fed back into the Holoportation application to enable self-optimization and adaptive operations.

7.3 Integration with Kubeflow Pipelines

Kubeflow Pipelines serve as the backbone of ML workflows in the cloud, enabling the modular design of data pipelines. As described in Deliverable D3.5 “Final prototype of the inclusion of AIOps and distributed intelligence in the system” and observed in Figure 2, we can see the basic Kubeflow Pipelines Data Flow and control:

Figure 2 Kubeflow Pipelines logic structure with Control Loop

The key features included in the architecture are:

Reproducibility: Every step in the pipeline, from data preprocessing to model deployment, is version-controlled and reproducible, ensuring consistency across deployments.

Scalability: Pipelines can handle large-scale datasets and scale computational resources dynamically, supporting the increasing demands of network operations.

Automation: Tasks such as hyperparameter tuning, model validation, and deployment are automated, reducing manual intervention and enabling faster iterations.

Observability: Built-in tracking and logging features allow operators to monitor pipeline execution, diagnose failures, and optimize workflow performance.

By linking the data aggregation process with Kubeflow Pipelines, the architecture ensures that data flows seamlessly into the ML lifecycle, maintaining high throughput and quality at every stage. This integration creates a feedback loop between the edge and cloud, enabling the continuous refinement of models and adaptive network optimization.

8 Data Aggregation applied in a 6G Self-Optimisation Architecture

Statistical data aggregation is fundamental in the 6G Enablers-AI hybrid architecture as it transforms raw, different data into meaningful actions. This process ensures that both cloud and edge operations are optimized by providing a structured representation of data that can be used for monitoring, decision-making, and ML model improvement. Aggregating data at multiple granularity levels—such as by time, spatial zones, or system components—enables effective pattern recognition, outlier detection, and resource optimization. Additionally, aggregation reduces noise in raw data, allowing for the identification of underlying trends and the derivation of robust metrics for operational intelligence.

As described in depth Deliverable “D5.5 Final prototype for data aggregation for self-optimization processes on network operations”, Empirical Cumulative Distribution Function (EC-CDF) provides a non-parametric way to represent the distribution of aggregated data, allowing system operators to understand the cumulative probability of values below a given threshold. It is particularly useful for detecting deviations, such as service level agreement (SLA) violations, and for assessing system performance metrics over time.

8.1 Monitoring, Aggregation and Decision Closed Loop Design

The closed-loop design integrates monitoring, aggregation, and decision-making into a continuous cycle that enables adaptive, self-optimizing operations. This loop consists of three interconnected stages:

Monitoring:

Real-time data from the Kubernetes cloud server (e.g., host and Kubernetes metrics) and edge telemetry sources (e.g., Holoportation application, Prometheus server) is continuously collected.

Observability backends and dashboards visualize aggregated metrics and provide operators with actionable insights into system performance, such as latency distributions, resource utilization, and SLA compliance.

Aggregation:

Raw telemetry is processed through statistical aggregation pipelines to create summaries at various levels of granularity:

In the cloud, metrics are aggregated using EC-CDF to detect deviations in SLA adherence and identify performance bottlenecks. At the edge, percentile calculations and rolling averages enable rapid detection of local anomalies, such as excessive resource usage or application instability. Aggregated data is then

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fed into the Feature Store and offline store for model retraining, validation, and historical analysis.

Decision-Making:

Aggregated actions are fed into AI Ops entities for autonomous decision-making. For example: Predictive models detect trends in performance degradation and proactively allocate resources to prevent SLA breaches. Aggregated EC-CDF data inform policies for traffic rerouting or scaling decisions. Feedback from these decisions is looped back into the monitoring stage, enabling continuous optimization of both cloud and edge operations.

9 Conclusion

This deliverable has outlined the final design for data aggregation as a critical enabler of self-optimization in network operations. By unifying telemetry data from cloud and edge environments, the architecture facilitates seamless monitoring, aggregation, and decision-making processes within a closed-loop system. Key functionalities, including the use of statistical methods like EC-CDF, enhance the interpretability and utility of aggregated data. The integration of Kubeflow Pipelines ensures scalable, reproducible, and automated ML workflows that drive both real-time optimization and long-term model improvements. Ultimately, this design provides a resilient and scalable foundation for next-generation network operations, supporting the goals of adaptability, operational intelligence, and resource efficiency within the 6G Enablers-AI framework. Through this innovative approach, the project contributes to advancing the state of the art in network self-optimization, paving the way for robust and intelligent network infrastructures.